

Spectrophotometric Studies on the Complexes of 1:2:4-trihydroxyanthraquinone with Some Rare-Earth Salts

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Lanthanum, cerium, praseodymium, neodymium and samarium chlorides interact with 1:2:4-trihydroxyanthraquinone forming pink coloured complexes which have been studied spectrophotometrically. The wavelength of maximum absorption for the dye and the complexes were 480 and 520 m μ respectively. The concentration ranges, in which Lambert and Beer's law is applicable have been ascertained. The ratio in which the rare earth salt and the dye react to form the complexes, has been found to be 1:2 by Job's method and molar ratio method. The log of apparent stability constant for these complexes is 9.1 ± 0.2 .

Flumiani and Bajic¹ in their studies on the reactions of hydroxyanthraquinones, observed that 1:2:4-trihydroxyanthraquinone (purpurin) forms a dark violet normal salt with copper sulphate having the composition $(C_{14}H_8O_4(OH)_2O)_2Cu$. Korenman *et al.*² reported that purpurin can be used in the detection of scandium at pH 2-3 in the presence of yttrium, lanthanum, cerium and aluminium. Korenman and Kornakova³ investigated the complex formation of Zr^{4+} with purpurin. Yampol Skii⁴ mentioned the use of purpurin in the analysis of gallium and indium.

Chlorides of lanthanum, cerium, praseodymium, neodymium and samarium form pink coloured complexes with purpurin which find no mention in the existing literature. Spectrophotometric studies on these complexes are being presented in this communication.

PROCEDURE AND RESULTS

0.6405 gm. of 1:2:4-trihydroxyanthraquinone was dissolved in 05% ethanol in a 250 ml flask to obtain 0.01M solution. For preparing the standard solutions of the rare-earth salts, $LaCl_3$, $CeCl_3$, $PrCl_3$, $NdCl_3$ and $SmCl_3$ (A.R. samples, Chemistry Division, A.E.E., Bombay) were dissolved in double distilled water. The solutions were standardized⁵ by precipitating the rare-earth as oxalate, treating with dilute sulphuric acid and titrating the resulting oxalic acid with standard permanganate solution. Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 colorimeter was employed for spectrophotometric measurements.

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Vosburgh and Cooper method⁶ was used for wave length selection. Mixtures of purpurin and rare-earth salts were taken in the molar ratios of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 2:1 and 3:1 and pure purpurin solution, in ethanolic media and their optical densities measured in the visible range. The wavelength of maximum absorption was 520 m μ for the complexes with La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm and 480 m μ for the dye.

Lambert and Beer's law was found to hold good for 1:2, 1:3 and 1:4 mixtures (metal:dye) in the concentration ranges of 0.83×10^{-3} — 4.0×10^{-3} M, 0.25×10^{-3} — 3.0×10^{-3} M and 0.2×10^{-3} — 2.5×10^{-3} M, for La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm complexes.

Job's method⁷, performed at the wavelength of maximum absorption and using 0.1×10^{-3} M and 0.125×10^{-4} M solutions of the reactants, yielded the molar ratio of 1:2 (metal:dye).

Molar ratio method⁸ was used to confirm the results of Job's method. 3 ml portions of a rare-earth salt of the concentration of 0.1×10^{-3} or 0.125×10^{-4} M were taken in nine test-tubes to which varying volumes of an equimolar solution of the dye added, the total volume made 12 ml by adding requisite amount of ethanol and the optical densities of the mixtures determined. Similar concentrations of the dye were taken in nine test-tubes making the total volume 12 ml with ethanol and the optical densities measured. The difference in optical density was plotted against the volume of the dye and the ratio was found to be 1:2 (metal:dye). The same ratio emerged when a constant volume of the dye was used and varying volumes of the rare-earth salt solution mixed.

The log of apparent stability constant was calculated by the method of Dey and Banerji⁹ using Job's curves with optical density as the ordinate and the composition of the mixtures as abscissa and the value was found to be 9.1 ± 0.2 .

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